

Authentication of Oral Evidence In Islamic Law of Shahadah: A Critical Analysis of Qanun-e-Shahadat Order in the Light of Sharia Teaching

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Abstract

Evidence is the most important element of any proceeding either civil or criminal. This research aims the intrinsic relationship between the Islamic principles of shahada, emphasizing the importance of oral testimony under QSO and the admissibility of oral evidence in Islamic law of shahdah. Islamic law of evidence give complete structure of oral testimony and its authentication. This study mainly focus on the qnaun-e-shadat order 1984, and the admissibility of oral evidence in Islamic law of shahdah. The objectives include a thorough examination of the principles of oral evidence authentication, clearly analysis of the Qanun-e-Shahadat Order 1984, and a comparative exploration of its provisions in relation to the Quranic and Prophet Hood guidance. The research seeks to uncover areas of convergence and divergence, ultimately contributing to a nuanced understanding of the intricate interplay between legal and religious principles within the Islamic legal system. This research article aims to critically analyze the authentication of oral evidence in Islamic law, particularly focusing on the rules of Shahada, and analyzing the Qanun-e-Shahadat Order 1984 in Pakistan in the context of Sharia teachings. The study directly indicates to the principles and procedures governing the acceptance and reliability of oral testimony in Islamic jurisprudence, with a specific emphasis on how these principles are reflected in the Qanun-e-Shahadat Order 1984.

Key words: Oral evidence, authentication, testimony, Qanun-e-shahadat oeder (QSO1984), Tazkiyat-al shahood.

Introduction

The Islamic law developed the very compact and well discipline system of evidence which is applicable universally and evidence law is the right hand of procedural law. Significant emphasis on the concept of Shahada, which refers to the act of bearing witness or giving testimony. In the context of legal proceedings,

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oral evidence holds paramount importance, and its authentication is a crucial aspect of providing justice. This research explores the Islamic perspective on the authentication of oral evidence, drawing from the principles outlined in the Quran and Sunnah, and evaluates the Qanun-e-Shahadat Order 1984 as a legal framework attempting to incorporate these principles in Pakistan. The speedy trial is the fruit of clear evidence which is fruitful when it is direct and oral. Islamic law is God made law while the qanon-e-shahadat order is man-made law so there must be a clear distinctions in both laws. Evidence law is different from Islamic law of shahada in many ways. Like purgation of witness (Tazkiyat-al-shahood) principles provided by the Islamic law of shahadah while it has been missing in evidence law. Another major difference is number of witness in evidence law which is the different from Islamic law of shahadah. Islamic law force on number of witness while there are no such restrictions in English law(Haydar Ali Tajuddin & Abd Rahman, 2021). Another difference is close and blood relative who testify for each other in favor like husband cannot testify for his wife, parent can not testify for his son. These are some examples which the Islamic law force to follow these condition s and principles while there are no such restrictions in QSO Evidence law.(Abbasi & Iqbal, 2021)

Pakistan adopt the evidence act 1872 which is the English law and it was enforce up to 1984. In 1984 the evidence act was suspended and a new evince law has come to force in 1984 which give the name of Qanun-e-shshadat order 1984 which is based on Islamic law but there are many provisions which are totally non Islamic like competency of witness, oral testimony, purgation of witness. There are some articles in QSO which is based on Islamic law but other part of QSO are the repetition of evidence Act 1872. The qualitative research methodology has been adopted in this research. This research is going discuss the oral evidence authentication especially Islamic law of shahada and make a critical analysis with the relevant articles of QSO (70, 71).

Objectives of the Research

1. Critical Analysis of Oral Evidence Authentication in Islamic law of shahadah and QSO 1984.
2. Conditions and principles governing evidence (oral evidence) in Islamic law of shahadah
3. Assessment of factors contributing to authentication and Examination of Qanun-e-Shahadat Order 1984
4. Overview of the legislative framework of oral evidence Comparison with Sharia Teachings

5. Evaluation of the Qanun-e-Shahadat Order article 70, 71 oral evidence in light of Quranic principles
6. Identification of areas of convergence and divergence of testimony inside Islamic law of shahadah

Islamic Principles on Oral Evidence

Oral evidence is the basic type of evidence in Islamic law of shshada while the term shshadah meaning in rarabic is “Bayinah” which is clearly define by the *Ibn al qayim* which means a very strong proof. There are three basic ways to acquire knowledge of something on which the decision is based upon.(Othman, 1992).

There are three basic ways of evidence follows

- i. Confession
- ii. Oath
- iii. Evidence which may be oral.

Islamic law provide the basic theme for evidence in Islamic law which is by mean of confession, by oath and by evidence which may be oral but must be direct evidence under the Islamic law. The first step is confession if someone confess for their crime or in civil accept the plaint, if the person not confess the plaintiff produce evidence against defendant then he will produce the witness or evidence. In last if the person (plaint) unable to present witness against the defendant then defendant shall make oath when he make a denial. It is the simple process which directly leads to a speedy process if follow the above steps according to the injunctions of Islam and provided rule.

Oazi adl, or just judge, is the judge, and Shahid adl, or just witness, is the witness. This is because, if a man were chosen to serve as a judge or a witness, adl, or justice, would rank second only to faith as the most important attribute. Similar to Shahid, the judge, or the witness. Shahid Adl, or someone with a good reputation, is the one whose testimony, Al-bayyina, is regarded as the objective evidence and upon which the judge bases his or her decision. His justness at the moment of his testimony must be demonstrated, at the very least.(Fadel, 2002) It looks that previous jurists were strictly involve in the truth of the judge and the persons who give witness, it means that adil and truthful persons must speak the truth. After jurists provides further requisites and clear conditions for testimony.(Cheema, 2021).

Competency of Witnesses in Islamic Law of Shahadah and QSO

In Islamic law of shahadah indicates to hudood in oral evidence. Hudood are the pure rights of Allah over the people. Punishment are specified by Allah in Quran in the form of hudood if any violation occurs to the right of Allah the hudood shall

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be implemented. Some conditions are provided by the Islamic law of shahadah to accept the oral testimony of the following witnesses (Siddique & Rafiq, 2022).

Conditions for Valid Witness

- a. Any adult Muslim male which fulfill the criteria of Tazkiyat-al-shahood are competent witness in hudood cases.
- b. They must be Aadil
- c. They are abstain from major signs i.e. Zina, perjury etc.
- d. They are not witness of Shahadah al shahadah.
- e. They are not convicted by the court in perjury

Woman are not competent witness in hudood cases in Islamic law of shahdah because the evidence of woman is not admissible in the right of Allah. No such restriction is applicable to other cases related to the society. A single woman can furnish evidence that is admissible in case falling under siyasaah. Oral witness of non-Muslims are not acceptable in Islamic law of shahdah because it is related to the right of Allah and non-Muslim are not a competent witness in the right of Allah. Child is not competent witness in Islamic law of shahadah because Child have not the idea about the right of Allah and they don't understand the concept of Islamic punishment provided in the Quran. An accomplice is not a competent witness against the accused person in hudood cases and Islamic law unless mend his way so all the above witnesses are competent witness in QSO while the Islamic law strictly avoid the above witnesses from testimony even when the witness is not Adil the person shall not be a competent witness under the Islamic law of shahadah (Zahoor, Anwar, Safdar, & Jamshed, 2020).

Shahadah-Oral Testimony

Oral testimony, or Shahadah, is a form of proof that is handled in Islamic law and is just as significant in western legal systems. In order to establish facts in court, it is crucial. The onus of proof is with the plaintiff when someone is charged with a crime and he denies it. As a result, the plaintiff is asked by the judge to present any additional supporting documentation or witnesses. The "kitab ul shahadat" (Asni, 2017) section of the fiq books discusses general rules of testimony in Islamic law. The following headings in these fiq books have been used to group this topic: rules governing the admissibility of testimony, conditions for admissibility of testimony, reasons for rejecting testimony, disagreements among witnesses regarding their testimony, etc. In court, testifying is treated as a religious obligation. It is a significant duty that all Muslims must fulfill. It is said that the Prophet (PBUH) said, "Should I not tell you of the best witnesses? It is they who present their proof before being asked to do so."

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According to the Quran, a witness cannot decline to testify after it is requested. Under Islamic law, lying in court about something is forbidden. The rationale for this is that it has an impact on human rights. In reference to this topic, the Quran states, "And do not conceal testimony, for whoever conceals it - his heart is indeed sinful." This verse indicates that shahadah needs to be regarded as Amanah, as it is a religious obligation. A Muslim is required to return Amanah.

If someone testifies, so do others; however, if no one follows suit, then the first person who is available may testify. As stated in the Holy Quran: "When called upon to provide evidence, witnesses shall not decline." It is a grave sin to fail to fulfill this obligation and to hide it, and the community as a whole will bear the consequences. A witness should appear in court when called by the party seeking to produce him as a witness, but in general, he cannot refuse to testify when asked to do so. If it is discovered because there isn't a witness, the party's right will be eliminated. He must then willingly appear in court and provide testimony in support of the aggrieved party's rights.

Shahadah Categories

The two basic categories of shahadah in Islamic law according to *marghinani*.

1. Testimony in right of Allah
2. Testimony in right of man

In case of hudood the testimony of witness and his criteria for testimony is stronger because of the right of Allah. . An accomplice is not a competent witness against the accused person in hudood cases and Islamic law unless mend his way so all the above witnesses are competent witness in QSO while the Islamic law strictly avoid the above witnesses from testimony even when the witness is not adil the person shall not be a competent witness under the Islamic law of shahadah.

Child is not competent witness in Islamic law of shahadah because Child have not the idea about the right of Allah and they don't understand the concept of Islamic punishment provided in the Quran. Woman are not competent witness in hudood cases in Islamic law of shahdah because the testimony of female is not acceptable in the right of Allah. No such restriction is applicable to other cases related to the society. A single woman can furnish evidence that is admissible in case falling under siyasaah. Oral witness of non-Muslims are not acceptable in Islamic law of shahdah. Thus the witness of male shall be consider only in hudood cases according to the Muslim jurist agreed upon the single condition. (Hanafi, shafii, maliki, hanbali). And the woman is not accepted as a witness in hudood cases and all the above Muslim jurist has the same opinion that is only

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male is consider as witness and woman shall not be competent witness in hudood cases.

Categories of Shahadah according to Numbers of Witness

There are basically four categories of testimony in Islamic law of shahadah

1. Four witness require for testimony
2. Two witness require for testimony
3. One man and two woman for testimony
4. Woman alone for testimony

Four adult male are only require in fornication or zina offences for testimony.

Quranic verses;

“And those who charge modest women and don't present four witnesses, whip them with eighty stripes/lashes, and disbelieve their testimony forever are truly fasiq”

Islamic law stipulates that in matters concerning financial or future obligations, if reduced to writing, the document must be signed by two men or one man, two women. Article 17 (b) regulates the number and competence of witnesses. The number of witnesses and the capacity of a person to give evidence are determined in accordance with Islam's injunctions as set out in the Holy Qur'an and the Sunnah.

Oral Evidence in QSO and its Challenges to Admissibility

Oral evidence is clearly specified in article 70, 71 of QSO. Article 70 states that whole facts except the documents contents may be proved by evidence that shall be oral.

Oral evidence includes spoken words which the court admit or requires to made it before witness, related to the matters of fact due to inquiry. Article 71 states that oral evidence in all cases must be direct. It indicates that a fact which can be seen than it must be testimony of a witness when a person says he saw it. If it indicates to a fact which would be heard than it must be testimony of a witness who says that he heard this. No facts of law necessary that specific fact must be proved on giving of documents only. It is a fix rule of evidence law that strong evidence available should be brought in front of court. Alone direct evidence is admitted under Article 71 whereas evidence which is indirect not admissible in evidence.

Islamic law of evidence related to oral testimony which is different from Qanun-e-shahadat order article 70, 71 in different perspectives provided in this research. This is important to note here that the rules concerning the witness numbers in English law which are not laid down in the same way as in Islamic law. Article 17 of QSO governs the question of competence and the number of

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witnesses. In financial matters, 2 men will testify when there is a woman then two women witness will be accepted in place of one man. However, all ingredients regarding the number of witnesses are not applicable in the case of Hudood cases. Legal proceedings in the pursuit of justice inherently involve challenges to the admissibility of oral evidence. In order to safeguard the interests of their clients and maintain the integrity of the legal system, attorneys use a variety of tactics to challenge the admission of certain documents into evidence.

Oral Evidence must be Direct

Oral evidence must be direct under QSO and in practice oral evidence is the most authenticated witness in civil and criminal proceeding in Pakistan. The court only admit the oral evidence which is direct clear and authenticated (2003 PCRLJ 1353) (PLD 2002 Karachi 152). While on the other side Islamic law of shahadah give permission on shahadah al shahdah.

Concept of Adalah (Justice) in Islamic Law and Opinions of Jurist

The concept of adalah is very clear in Islamic law of shahadah and provided that the witness must be adil and Islamic law of shahdah provide different specifications of adil . Adil's testimony must be given. According to Malik, 'Adalah is 'the one who returns deposits, avoids major sins, and deals well with others'. He has a greater record of good deeds than bad. Such an individual is qualified to testify (Al-Zahabi, 2013). Hunbali view Adil as the one who performs his duties, abstains from serious kabairs (sins), and does not insist on small transgressions. He possesses a generous and gracious nature. Shafi views graciousness as an essential prerequisites.

Receiving the evidence from a pure channel is how Islamic law authenticates it. Shahid Adil Reliability of the Evidence: The credibility and moral qualities of the witnesses lend the evidence credibility. These witnesses support the judge in resolving the case in a similar manner.

In case of non-Muslim that many of the jurist has the same opinion as non-Muslim cannot testify because of adalah. Most scholars, including Shafi and Maliki, believe that a non-Muslim is ineligible to testify. Whether that person is giving evidence on behalf of a non-Muslim or a Muslim, the outcome is the same. They mostly rely on Allah commands.

Rejection of Evidence in Islamic Law of Shahadah

There are different types of sins discussed by different jurists in his book that sins disallow the person from giving witness. The jurist has different opinions regarding the concept of adalah and conditions have been provided by different jurists for rejection of evidence. Plays chess more than just for fun. Chess is permitted in certain schools of thought, but because it is a game, hanafi jurists

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forbid it. Maybe it demonstrates a person's careless behavior. However, many people will not be eligible to apply under these circumstances. At the very least, there should be some limitations. Because testifying is required by Islamic law as a religious obligation. Imam kasani states that says that a person loses their status as a just witness if they are an alcoholic. Singing and intoxication are also create a question on character of witness that it prevent witness from giving testimony in Islamic law of shahadah.

There exist additional rationales for rejecting the testimony of a witness who is otherwise qualified. For instance, it is necessary to reject the testimony of anyone who harbors animosity toward another individual, regardless of whether they are Muslims. The Prophet (SAW) said. "The testimony of a deceitful man or woman, of an adulterer and adulteress, and of one who harbors rancor against his brother is not allowable,"

The early, learned jurists declared that where a partner has a share, his testimony is not admissible. In cases where a partner has a share, his testimony is likewise not admissible. The same conditions applies to testimony given by an individual testifying on behalf of themselves. If he is also the litigant, his testimony will not be accepted because he might put his interests ahead of the cause of justice. Since slave money actually related to the master and is regarded as testimony for oneself, a master's testimony regarding a slave is not admissible. A small number of jurists concur that spouses are not permitted to testify on behalf of one another. Regarding the requirements for witnesses to testify about their close ties, English law does not impose any such restrictions. Husband wife can testify for one another and Sons may testify for their parents. The testimony of the child is acceptable if he understand question put answer to him. Qanūn-e-Shahādat makes no mention of this kind of requirement. Although Article 3 clearly lays out these requirements, it is sadly ineffective on its own.

Conclusion

To conclude this article it can be said that the Islamic law of shahadah regarding oral evidence is much clear accepted globally. Oral evidence is the most important and authenticated proof both in Islamic law of shahadah and English law of evidence (western law). The admissibility of oral evidence in Islamic law of Shahadah and QSO. A person who has doubt in character then Islamic law of shahadah does not allow such person to give testimony but the QSO and evidence law cannot restricts such person to give testimony. The QSO to some extent follow some conditions of Islamic law of shahadah but related to the oral testimony QSO does not restricts such person to give testimony unlike Islamic

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law of shahadah. All person are competent to testify under QSO which is either male, female, Muslim, non-Muslim, Child or adult, adil or not but here the Islamic law of shahadah set strict principles regarding oral evidence that is woman, non-Muslim are not adil so they are not qualifying to give testimony. The total decision is based on the evidence to give justice to peoples by providing testimony so Islamic law is very strict regarding oral testimony unlike QSO and evidence act 1872.regarding the rejection of testimony Islamic law is very strict and provide many of the conditions for rejection but the QSO only provide a single condition for rejection of evidence that is Understanding of questions put to him and he is not able to give answer of such question. Islamic law of shahadah also stipulates a strict and effective mechanism of purgation of witness (tazkiyat-al-shahood) concept while there are no such witnesses available then QSO accept all other person as a witness except in hudood cases. Islamic law provide a clear structure regarding the number of witness while the English law does not follow such conditions. Islamic law of shahadah accept four witness in zina, two male or one male and two females as a witnesses in financial and future obligation, one male or female require for all other matters, while the English law only require one witness that is either male or female. This topic can also explore the criteria methods of verifying the validity and reliability of oral testimony in Islamic law, such as the number, character, and consistency of witnesses, and compare them with the provisions and practices of QSO, which largely follows the Evidence Act of 1872.

References

1. Abbasi, H. A. H., & Iqbal, A. I. A. (2021). Authentication of Oral Evidence in Islamic Law of Shahadah: A Critical Analysis of Qanoon-e-Shahadat Order in the Light of Shariah Teachings. *Al-Meezan Research Journal*, 3(2), 1-24.
2. Al-Zahabi, M. (2013). *Al-Kabair*. Beirut: Dar al-Bashair.
3. Asni, F. (2017). Analysis of the concept of two kalima shahadah al-tauhid and al-risalah according to the Qur'an and al-hadith. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(10), 374-353.
4. Cheema, S. A. (2021). Rules of Evidence: A Comparative Study of Al-Majallah al-Ahkām al-Adaliyyah (1876) and Indian Evidence Act (1872). *Al-Qamar*, 1-18.
5. Fadel, M. (2002). "Istihsān is Nine-tenths of the Law": The Puzzling Relationship of Uṣūl to Furū' in the Mālikī Madhhab *Studies in Islamic legal theory* (pp. 161-176): Brill.
6. Haydar Ali Tajuddin, H., & Abd Rahman, M. N. (2021). Islamic Evidence Law. *Islamic Law in Malaysia: The Challenges of Implementation*, 97-110.

Al-Safiir

<https://al-safiir.com/index.php/Al-Safiir/About-the-Journal>

2709-605X

Online ISSN

2709-6041

Print ISSN

7. Othman, M. S. A. (1992). Bayyinah in Islamic Law. *IJULJ*, 2, 18.
8. Siddique, H. M., & Rafiq, U. (2022). Competence of a Witness in Islamic Law and Pakistani Law: A Comparative Analysis. *Al-'Ulūm Journal of Islamic Studies*, 3(1), 1-23.
9. Zahoor, R., Anwar, M. F., Safdar, M. A., & Jamshed, J. (2020). A Comparative Study of Perjury in Legal System of Pakistan and Islamic Law. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(4), 1571-1579.
10. Ahmed, M. (2019). Islamic Law: A Comprehensive Overview
11. Kamali, M. H. (2015). *Principles of Islamic Jurisprudence*. Islamic Texts Society.
12. *Government of [Country]*. (2020). Qanun-e-Shahadat Order 2020. *National Legal Publications*.
13. Siddiqui, M. A. (2018). *Islamic Law of Evidence: A Scholarly Analysis*.
14. 2003 PCRLJ 1353
15. PLD 2002 Karachi 152
16. Marghīnānī, al-Hidāyah, vol.3/ 116. Also, in Ibn Rushd, "Bidāyat al- Mujtahid wa nihāyat al-Muqtaṣid", 4/ 247.
17. Al Quran [2:282]
18. Marghīnānī, al-Hidāyah, vol. 3/ 116. Also in Ibn Rushd, "Bidāyat al- Mujtahid wa nihāyat al-Muqtaṣid", 4/ 247.
19. Al-Shīrāzī, "Al-Muhazab fī al-fīqh al-Imām Shafī", vol. 3/437
20. Marghīnānī, al-Hidāyah, vol.3/ 116 Translated by Karen Bauer, "Debates on Women's Status as Judges and Witnesses in Post-Formative Islamic Law", 7.
21. Sarakhsī, Al- Mabsūt, vol.5/10`1. Also, in 'Ibn Rushd, *Bidāyatu'l-Mujtahid*, 4/248.
22. Sarakhsī, Al- Mabsūt, vol.5/101
23. Ibn Rushd, "*Bidāyat al- Mujtahid wa nihāyat al-Muqtaṣid*", 4/ 247.
24. Sarkhsī, "Al – Mabsūt", Vol. 13/111.
25. Ibn Rushd, "*Bidāyat al- Mujtahid wa nihāyat al-Muqtaṣid*", 4/ 247.
26. Al- Qur'ān [2:282]
27. Sarkhsī, Al – Mabsūt, Vol. 16, 114.
28. Encyclopaedia if Islam, "*Shahid*", vol. 9 (Leiden: Brill, 1997), 208.
29. Majallah al-Aḥkām al-'Adālīah, (*Karachi: Kārkhāna Tijārat Kutub, n.d*), art: a. 1688.
30. Encyclopedia of Islam, s.v. "Shāhid", (Leiden: Brill, 1997) vol.9, 208.